

Towards Inclusive Search: Integrating Language Complexity in Information Retrieval

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1. Abstract

Existing accessibility strategies tend to focus on technical compatibility and assistive technologies, yet the linguistic dimension remains largely unaddressed at the system level. As such, the varying comprehensibility of search results is a silent barrier that continues to affect equitable information access, even when technical and navigational accessibility standards are met.

This contribution outlines a conceptual approach to inclusive search, arguing for the integration of language complexity assessments into search engines. While conventional search engines optimize for topical relevance and authority signals, accessibility must be integrated as an equally critical dimension of information quality to address diverse user needs. Recent advances in neural text difficulty estimation suggest that automatic scoring of web content along a continuous complexity scale is feasible (Ermakova & Kamps, 2024; Filighera et al., 2019; Shardlow et al., 2021). Transformer-based models, such as derivatives of BERT and RoBERTa, have demonstrated promising capabilities in predicting linguistic complexity, even across multiple languages and domains (Lee & Vajjala, 2022).

Supporting inclusive search requires addressing linguistic complexity as a structural barrier, not merely a user-side deficit. This entails rethinking indexing, ranking, and result presentation with accessibility as a guiding principle. By integrating complexity-aware scoring, relevance can be redefined to consider both topical alignment and comprehensibility. Interfaces may offer adjustable filters for language difficulty, indicate approximate proficiency levels required (as used in foreign language education), or use Natural Language Generation to produce alternative formulations tailored to users' needs.

Inclusion should not rely on fixed user groups but instead dynamically support individual abilities. Personalization must remain transparent and optional; simplification should clarify, not distort. Inclusive systems can also foster learning by providing accessible entry points while gradually encouraging engagement with more complex material provided that such progression is actively supported.

Ethical challenges include fidelity in generated content, potential reinforcement of stereotypes, and preserving user agency. Evaluation should go beyond technical criteria to assess cognitive and linguistic usability, ideally through participatory testing.

Traditional relevance models focus on topic alignment, keyword matching, and popularity signals, resulting in a narrow definition of what constitutes a 'relevant' result. This contribution proposes expanding this definition to incorporate cognitive accessibility as a core dimension of relevance. Rather than treating comprehensibility as a secondary filter applied after topical matching, we argue for an integrated relevance framework where content is considered truly relevant only when it meets both topical and cognitive accessibility requirements. This requires (1) multi-dimensional scoring combining topical precision and linguistic accessibility, (2) recognition that authoritative source may be inaccessible, thus justifying alternative renditions, and (3) adapting to users' abilities without requiring self-identification. Reframing relevance through this inclusive lens enables search engines to become

equitable knowledge mediators – bridging gaps rather than reinforcing them through algorithmically-perpetuated linguistic barriers.

2. Presentation Structure

The presentation will briefly outline key ideas from the abstract, followed by an open discussion to reflect on additional challenges, perspectives, and design considerations for inclusive search systems.

3. References

Ermakova, L. and Kamps, J. (2024) ‘Complexity-Aware Scientific Literature Search: Searching for Relevant and Accessible Scientific Text’, in G.M.D. Nunzio et al. (eds) *Proceedings of the Workshop on DeTermIt! Evaluating Text Difficulty in a Multilingual Context @ LREC-COLING 2024*. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL, pp. 16–26. Available at: <https://aclanthology.org/2024.determin-1.2/>.

Filighera, A., Steuer, T. and Rensing, C. (2019) ‘Automatic text difficulty estimation using embeddings and neural networks’, in *Transforming Learning with Meaningful Technologies: 14th European Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning, EC-TEL 2019, Delft, The Netherlands, September 16--19, 2019, Proceedings 14*. Springer, pp. 335–348.

Lee, J. and Vajjala, S. (2022) ‘A Neural Pairwise Ranking Model for Readability Assessment’, in S. Muresan, P. Nakov, and A. Villavicencio (eds) *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL 2022*. Dublin, Ireland: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 3802–3813. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.findings-acl.300>.

Shardlow, M. et al. (2021) ‘SemEval-2021 Task 1: Lexical Complexity Prediction’, in A. Palmer et al. (eds) *Proceedings of the 15th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation (SemEval-2021)*. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2021.semeval-1.1>.